

STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF SCHOOL COUNSELLORS' ROLE IN FINANCIAL LITERACY AND DEBT AWARENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EKITI STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study examined secondary school students' perceptions of the role of school counsellors in promoting financial literacy covering budgeting, saving, spending, and money management and debt awareness in Ekiti State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was employed with a sample of 200 students. Findings indicated that students held moderately positive perceptions of their counsellors' involvement, with saving and money management being the most recognized areas. Regression analysis revealed that counsellor-led financial literacy initiatives significantly predicted students' debt awareness. The study concludes that school counsellors are significant in shaping adolescents' financial abilities and recommends the structured integration of financial literacy into school counselling programs to develop debt-aware behaviours

Keyword: Financial Literacy, Debt Awareness, Budgeting, Money Management, School Counsellor.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving global economy, the ability to manage personal finances, understand economic systems, and make informed financial decisions has become a core life skill. For adolescents and young adults, particularly those in Sub-Sahara Africa like Nigeria, financial literacy and debt awareness are critical for navigating the financial realities of adulthood. Despite the increasing complexity of financial systems and the early exposure of present day's youth to credit facilities, digital payments, and peer-driven consumption habits, financial literacy remains grossly underdeveloped among secondary school students in Nigeria (Adeleke & Igbinedion, 2023; Salami & Umeh, 2022). This shortfall in economic understanding among youths raises concerns, especially as young Nigerians are growing up in a country facing persistent inflation, economic instability, and rising household indebtedness (Nwachukwu & Daramola, 2022; Ogundele, 2022).

Despite growing recognition of the importance of financial literacy, there remains a significant gap in understanding the specific role of school counsellors in fostering this competency among adolescents in Nigeria. While studies have examined financial literacy programs in tertiary institutions and non-governmental interventions (Eze & Onwe, 2022), limited empirical attention

has been given to how school-based guidance and counselling services shape students' financial literacy and debt-related attitudes during their formative years. This oversight is notable given that secondary school represents a critical period for financial socialisation, where lifelong money habits and attitudes toward debt are often established (Mancone, Tosti, Corrado, Spica, Zanon, & Diotaiuti, 2024). Furthermore, students' own perceptions of counsellors' effectiveness in this domain remain largely unexplored, creating a disconnect between policy recommendations and on-the-ground counselling practices. This study therefore sought to address this void by investigating students' perceptions of the role of school counsellors in promoting financial literacy and debt awareness, thereby contributing actionable insights for strengthening life-skills education within the Nigerian secondary school system.

Debt awareness involves understanding the implications of borrowing, managing repayments, avoiding debt traps, and evaluating the long-term impact of indebtedness (Lusardi & Tufano, 2015). This competency is especially critical during adolescence, a formative period when values, habits, and identities begin to crystallize. Yet, in Nigerian secondary schools, these skills are rarely taught in a structured way and are often fragmented across subjects rather than presented as an integrated life skill (Eze & Onwe, 2022). This gap is alarming as adolescents, already making basic financial decisions, are increasingly exposed to fintech and digital credit, heightening their risk of financial missteps without proper guidance (Nwachukwu & Daramola, 2022).

In other not misstep in financial decision, the knowledge and skills in financial literacy is required to make informed and effective decisions with all of one's financial resources which serves as the fundamental defense against such risks that accrue (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau, 2019; Kaiser & Lusardi, 2024). This study posits that debt awareness is directly cultivated through mastery of its core components such as budgeting, saving, responsible saving and money management. Budgeting, as proactive income allocation, builds foresight to reduce unplanned borrowing. Saving on the other hand, establishes a financial buffer to diminish reliance on high-cost credit. Also, Responsible spending acts as a behavioral guard against accruing unnecessary debt through disciplined consumption. Finally, Money management integrates these practices, translating knowledge into daily habits and fostering the overall discipline needed to recognize and avoid debt traps (Kaiser et al., 2022; Xiao & Porto, 2017). In this context, the school counselling unit emerges as a strategically positioned, yet underutilized, resource for bridging this educational gap and equipping students with these essential competencies.

In this context, the school counselling unit emerges as a strategically positioned, yet underutilized, resource for bridging this educational gap. While Nigerian school counsellors have traditionally focused on academic and career guidance, their mandate and training in life skills education uniquely equip them to address students' holistic development, including financial wellbeing (Adepoju & Alabi, 2023). However, the specific role of counsellors in delivering financial literacy instruction and shaping students' debt awareness remains inadequately explored, particularly from the student perspective. Understanding how students perceive this role is a critical first step in effectively leveraging counselling services to build a financially capable generation.

Therefore, grounded in Social Cognitive Theory—which posits that learning occurs through the interaction of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors—this study investigates secondary school students' perceptions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. It specifically aimed to:

1. Examine students' perceptions of school counsellors' involvement in promoting financial literacy.
2. Assess the relationship between the core financial literacy components (budgeting, saving, spending, money management) and students' debt awareness. 3.
3. Determine the extent to which counsellor-led financial literacy initiatives predict students' debt awareness.

Identify which of the financial literacy components are most emphasized by counsellors, according to student perceptions.

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Many secondary school students in sub-sahara Africa, including those in Nigeria, are increasingly exposed to financial decisions like spending, saving, and even borrowing without proper guidance or education. Despite the growing importance of financial literacy and the risks of poor debt management among youths, schools often lack structured financial education programs. School counsellors, who are well-positioned to offer life skills training, rarely focus on financial topics, and it is unclear how students perceive their role in this area. School counsellors, who are well-positioned to offer life skills training, rarely focus on financial topics, and it is unclear how students perceive their role in this area. Previous research indicates that counsellors and trainees often face structural and workload-related challenges in effectively discharging their responsibilities (Owodunni & Olaoye, 2018), which may partly explain why financial literacy is not prioritized in secondary school counselling. This lack of clarity creates a gap in understanding how counselling services can support students' financial awareness. This study addresses that gap by exploring students' perceptions of how school counsellors contribute to their financial literacy and debt awareness.

1.1.2 Research Questions

1. What are students' perceptions of the role of school counsellors in promoting financial literacy in secondary schools in Ekiti State?
2. What is the relationship between financial literacy components (budgeting, saving, spending, and money management) and students' debt awareness in secondary schools in Ekiti State?
3. To what extent do financial literacy (budgeting, saving, spending, and money management), as promoted through school counsellors, jointly predict students' debt awareness in secondary schools in Ekiti State??
4. Which financial literacy (budgeting, saving, spending and money management) are most emphasized by school counsellors, according to students in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW: Social Cognitive Theory

This study is anchored on Bandura's (1986) Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), which posits that learning and behaviour are shaped by the dynamic interplay of personal, behavioural, and environmental factors. In the context of this study, environmental factors such as: the school

environment and the counsellor serve as key influencers. Counsellors provide guidance, model responsible financial behaviour, and create a supportive setting for learning.

Also, component of personal factors represent students' cognitive understanding that is, knowledge of budgeting, affective beliefs (attitude towards saving), and self-efficacy (confidence in managing money) are central. On the other hand, behavioural factors include the practical application of financial skills, such as responsible spending and saving habits, that constitutes the behavioural outcome. SCT suggests that when school counsellors (environment) provide structured financial education, they help shape students' financial knowledge and attitudes (personal), which in turn influences their money management behaviours (behavioural), including their awareness and avoidance of debt. This theoretical lens provides a robust framework for understanding how counsellor-led initiatives can enhance financial literacy and debt awareness.

2.1 Conceptual Issues of *Debt Awareness*

Lusardi and Tufano (2009) defined the concept of debt awareness as an individual's knowledge, recognition, and appraisal of debt-related concepts. That is, how borrowing works, the cost of credit (interest and fees), the long-term consequences of default, and the behavioural signals that lead to risky borrowing (impulse buying and over-reliance on short-term credit). In youth and school contexts today, debt awareness focuses on whether young people understand credit choices they will face, the dangers of high-interest borrowing, and practical ways to avoid debt traps (CFPB, 2019; Kaiser & Lusardi, 2024).

Adolescence, in particular, represents a critical stage for financial socialization, as patterns and attitudes developed during this period often persist into adulthood (Mancone et al., 2024). Consequently, fostering debt awareness among secondary school students is not only a preventive measure against future financial vulnerability but also a foundation for cultivating responsible financial behaviours that support long-term economic stability. Young people who lack debt awareness are more likely to incur harmful forms of borrowing once they enter the consumer economy which varies from high-cost loans, unsecured debt or to make poor student-loan decisions (Brown et al., 2014). Conversely, stronger debt awareness is associated with better credit outcomes, lower likelihood of over-indebtedness, and more cautious use of credit products as young adults (CFPB, . 2019; Lusardi & Tufano, 2015).

Debt awareness is often conceptualized along three interrelated dimensions: factual knowledge, such as understanding interest rates and repayment schedules; risk perception, which reflects the ability to recognize the potential consequences of late or missed payments; and behavioural intent or attitude, which concerns an individual's willingness to avoid risky borrowing practices. Contemporary financial education initiatives aim to strengthen all three dimensions, recognizing that knowledge on its own is insufficient unless accompanied by heightened risk awareness and positive behavioural intentions. In other words, effective debt education requires not just teaching facts, but also reshaping perceptions and fostering practical habits that promote safer borrowing and money management (Kaiser & Lusardi, 2024; CFPB, 2019).

2.1.1 Financial Literacy and School Counsellors.

A study by Adeleke and Igbinedion (2023) in southwestern Nigeria found that while most students were actively making money-related decisions, such as managing pocket money and engaging in small informal trading, few had received any formal education on saving, budgeting, or debt. The study revealed that school counsellors were largely underutilized in this area, even though they were seen by students as trusted adults who could guide them. Students who received counselling that touched on life skills—including financial topics—showed significantly better money habits than their peers. Similarly, Chikwendu and Etim (2023) investigated the role of school-based financial literacy programs in Cross River State and found that group counselling and life skills workshops led by school counsellors improved students' budgeting behaviour and awareness of debt risks. The study emphasized that the school counselling unit should not be limited to academic and career advice, but should incorporate practical financial education aligned with students' daily realities.

In an era of mobile banking and fintech, even secondary school students are being exposed to credit and debt. Nwachukwu and Daramola (2022) reported that a growing number of Nigerian adolescents access mobile lending apps through their phones, sometimes borrowing without fully understanding repayment terms or long-term consequences. Alarming, some students considered borrowing normal—even admirable—because of peer pressure or a lack of knowledge. The researchers called for proactive engagement by school counsellors to curb the spread of unhealthy borrowing habits among young people. Another study by Ogundele (2022) highlighted the gap between digital exposure and financial readiness among Nigerian youths. It noted that while many teenagers are active users of mobile payment systems and online marketplaces, most do not understand interest rates, debt accumulation, or the importance of savings. The study advocated for the integration of digital financial literacy into school counselling services as a form of preventive education.

Overall, the emerging evidence underscores that school counsellors play a pivotal role in shaping students' financial literacy and debt awareness. Across different states in Nigeria, research consistently shows that when counsellors move beyond traditional academic and career guidance to incorporate life skills such as budgeting, saving, responsible spending, and understanding debt, students develop healthier financial behaviours and perceptions (Adeleke & Igbinedion, 2023; Chikwendu & Etim, 2023). In particular, counsellors are positioned as trusted adults who can bridge the gap between adolescents' digital exposure to money—through mobile banking and lending apps—and their limited understanding of financial risks (Nwachukwu & Daramola, 2022; Ogundele, 2022). This makes the counselling unit not just a support service but a strategic platform for preventive financial education, equipping students with both the knowledge and attitudes needed to navigate an increasingly complex financial environment.

2.1.2 Concept of Financial Literacy in Relation with Debt Awareness

Internationally, UNESCO (2023) released a global framework urging countries to adopt financial literacy as a critical life skill. Financial literacy is a multi-dimensional construct that includes financial knowledge (conceptual understanding), skills (budgeting, record-keeping), attitudes (prudence, delayed gratification), and behaviours (saving, responsible spending, debt avoidance). In empirical work and policy practice, the construct is often decomposed into the components used

in this study: budgeting, saving, spending (responsible spending), and money management (Kaiser & Lusardi 2024; Xiao & O'Neill, 2018).

A Budgeting and Debt Awareness

Budgeting has consistently been linked with debt avoidance and responsible financial behaviour. For instance, Xiao and Porto (2017) found that budgeting reduces reliance on credit and that individuals who actively budget their expenses are significantly less likely to rely on high-interest credit, as budgeting improves their foresight of repayment capacity. This authors later later argue that budgeting reduces reliance on credit (Xiao & Porto (2017)). A similar position is held by Babiarz and Robb (2014) whom emphasized that budgeting equips individuals with a sense of control over spending, reducing the likelihood of falling into consumer debt traps. Furthermore, Salami and Umeh (2022) examined financial education as a strategy for poverty reduction and discovered that students who received structured financial guidance demonstrated better financial habits and were more aware of long-term consequences of debt. The study emphasized the need to strengthen the guidance and counselling component of secondary school education, particularly in economically vulnerable regions. Bruhn, Garber, Koyama, and Zia (2022) reported that high school students who participated in school-based financial education programs that included budgeting modules demonstrated stronger financial decision-making skills and a lower tendency to incur debt compared to those without such exposure. his supports the idea that school-based financial literacy programs, including budgeting training, enhance students' awareness of debt risks and lead to reduced reliance on credit. Unfortunately, the annual budgetary allocation to education in Nigeria is not acceptable to all the education stakeholders. Faremi (2021) laid claimed that due to a dearth of comprehensive and poor budgetary allocation to education sector, corruption and mismanagement of public funds, school teachers' welfare has been badly neglected by the government as her responsibility in which as affected students' progress and academic performance, yearly . The reason was that the budgetary allocation to education annually is very poor compare to other countries, which cannot use to implement the various educational policies across all levels of education in Nigeria (Faremi & Owojuyigbe, 2023).

B Saving and Debt Awareness

According to Lusardi, Michaud, and Mitchell (2017), savings behaviour has been empirically tied to reduced debt exposure. This was evidence in the work that individuals with stronger saving habits are less vulnerable to shocks that may push them into debt, because savings provide a financial cushion (Lusardi et al., 2017). Likewise, Shim et al. (2010) found that young adults who practiced regular saving in adolescence had better credit outcomes and fewer debt-related problems in college.

More recently, Kaiser and Lusardi (2022) observed that financial education that emphasizes saving leads to more prudent borrowing choices, especially among youth in developing countries. For Nigerian students, building a culture of saving is critical to offsetting the growing trend of reliance on informal loans or family credit in times of need. Moreso, saving behaviors (forming emergency funds, goal-based saving) indirectly bolster debt awareness by reducing exposure to high-cost, short-term credit. Reviews of youth financial education show that saving is one of the easiest behaviors to move, and programs that build the habit of regular saving tend to report improved

understanding of when (and when not) to borrow—i.e., more realistic appraisals of credit risk (CFPB, 2019). This connotes that having behaviours strengthen financial cushions and appear to heighten students' sensitivity to the true costs of debt, though effects on borrowing decisions are smaller unless programs pair saving with explicit debt-cost instruction.

C Responsible Spending and Debt Awareness

Spending discipline is another critical determinant of debt risk. Prior research demonstrates a clear behavioral link to debt outcomes. For example, Norvilitis and Mendes-Da-Silva (2013) found that college students demonstrating greater delay of gratification—indicative of disciplined spending—reported lower levels of credit card debt and improved financial well-being. Correspondingly, Robb and Sharpe (2009) showed that, beyond income, spending behavior and financial knowledge significantly explain student debt accumulation. In Nigeria, Odia and Ogiedu (2013) highlighted that secondary school and university students with weak spending controls were more prone to fall into debt, often through mobile credit schemes. These findings affirm that teaching students about responsible spending is essential not only for budgeting success but also for cultivating awareness of the consequences of poor borrowing practices.

Similarly, a large behavioral literature links impulsive/compulsive spending to problematic debt; conversely, responsible spending (delay of gratification, planned purchases) is associated with lower debt risk (Black, 2007; Mueller et al., 2010). Empirical studies show self-control negatively predicts debt, while compulsive buying positively predicts indebtedness, implying that interventions which curb impulsive spending should raise awareness of debt risks and reduce costly borrowing.

D Money Management and debt Awareness

Money management (tracking income/expenses, goal setting, paying bills on time) is the integrator of budgeting, saving, and spending. A scoping review shows that day-to-day money-management habits are closely tied to psychological determinants (self-efficacy, planning) and to better credit behaviours or patterns aligned with higher debt awareness which ranges from noticing fee structures to anticipating late-payment penalties (Theepa et al., 2024). Also, in a programmatically study, in which youth interventions that combine tracking tools, simulations, and repeated reinforcement was found to produce stronger, more durable gains in financial behaviours than stand-alone lessons (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau, 2019). In effect the study also note that the programmatic designs most, likely to lift borrowing awareness, that is recognizing the long-run consequences of missed payments (CFPP, 2019).

Pinto, Parente, and Mansfield (2005) found that students who developed money management skills early were less likely to accumulate debt in higher education. In a more recent global study carried out by Kaiser, Lusardi, Menkhoff, and Urban (2022) confirmed that financial literacy interventions that strengthen money management competencies significantly improve debt awareness and reduce the risk of default. Furthermore, Although Chowa and Despard (2014) do not focus directly on debt attitudes, their findings demonstrate that strong money management behaviors such as managing pocket money effectively—are a key component of financial capability among African adolescents, suggesting a foundation for healthier financial attitudes, including toward debt.

Despite the increasing evidence supporting the involvement of school counsellors in financial education, there is limited empirical research specifically addressing students' perceptions of such roles, particularly in Nigeria. While existing studies have explored the effectiveness of financial literacy programs or the readiness of counsellors, very few have focused on how students themselves experience and interpret the guidance they receive in this domain. This study, therefore, contributes to closing that gap by investigating students' perceptions in Ekiti State. It adds to the growing body of knowledge supporting the integration of financial literacy into school counselling programs, with the goal of helping students become financially informed, debt-aware, and economically empowered adults

2.3 Conceptual Model of the Study

Fig 1: Conceptual Model for the Study

Self Developed Model

The model illustrates how counsellor-led financial literacy (an environmental factor) is designed to directly influence students' debt awareness and perception (a personal factor), with the ultimate goal of fostering responsible financial behaviour. In this model, the counsellor acts as the key environmental influence, providing guidance and modelling responsible behaviour. The components shapes students' personal factors, such as their knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy regarding debt. The desired result is a change in behavioural factors, leading to practical and responsible financial habits in secondary school.

In essence, this model posits that structured financial education from counsellors can enhance students' personal understanding and attitudes towards debt, which in turn empowers them to adopt healthier financial behaviours.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey design to examine students' perceptions of school counsellors' involvement in promoting financial literacy—covering budgeting, saving, spending, and money management—and debt awareness in secondary schools. A total of 200 students from public schools were selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, the *Students' Financial Literacy and Debt Awareness Questionnaire (SFLDAQ)*, which had two sections: students' perceptions of counsellors' involvement and measures of financial literacy components with debt awareness. The instrument showed good reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values of 0.82 for financial literacy and 0.80 for debt awareness. Questionnaires were administered and retrieved on the spot with school support. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics to summarize responses, Pearson correlation to test the relationship between financial literacy and debt awareness, and regression analyses to examine predictive and relative contributions of the financial literacy dimensions. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted

4 ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: What are students' perceptions of school counsellors' involvement in promoting financial literacy?

Table 4.1: Frequency distribution of students' perceptions of school counsellors' involvement in promoting financial literacy

Item	Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev
1	My school counsellor teaches us how to manage money wisely.	38	42	14	6	3.12	0.79
2	The counselling sessions have helped me understand the importance of saving.	41	40	13	6	3.16	0.81
3	I have learned how to budget from discussions with my school counsellor.	35	37	18	10	2.97	0.88
4	The school counsellor advises us on how to spend money responsibly.	39	40	15	6	3.12	0.80
5	I have been taught how to set financial goals (short- or long-term).	33	39	18	10	2.95	0.89
6	My school counsellor uses real-life examples when teaching about money.	36	38	17	9	3.01	0.87
7	We are encouraged to ask questions about personal finance during sessions.	37	36	19	8	3.01	0.85

Threshold= 2.50; Weighted Mean=3.05 (Agreed)

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of students' perceptions of school counsellors' involvement in promoting financial literacy. Overall, students reported moderately positive perceptions across all items. The highest-rated item was "*The counselling sessions have helped me understand the importance of saving*" (M = 3.16, SD = 0.81), while the lowest was "*I have been taught how to set financial goals (short- or long-term)*" (M = 2.95, SD = 0.89). This suggests that students generally acknowledge the role of counsellors in fostering saving and money management skills, although goal-setting appears less emphasized. The findings also show a weighted mean of 3.05 which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between financial literacy components (budgeting, saving, spending, and money management) and students' debt awareness in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

Table 4.2: Correlation matrix showing the relationship between financial literacy components (budgeting, saving, spending, and money management) and debt awareness

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Debt Awareness	Budgeting	Saving	Spending	Money Management
Debt Awareness	3.50	0.58	1.000				
Budgeting	3.57	0.55	0.207**	1.000			
Saving	3.45	0.67	0.157**	0.094	1.000		
Spending	3.23	0.78	0.341**	-0.140**	-0.039	1.000	
Money Management	3.50	0.61	0.419**	0.064	-0.115	0.103	1.000

Correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed).

The correlation matrix (Table 4.2) shows significant positive relationships between all financial literacy components and debt awareness. Debt awareness was most strongly associated with money management ($r = .419$, $p < .05$) and spending ($r = .341$, $p < .05$), indicating that students who demonstrate stronger abilities in handling money and responsible spending are more likely to be aware of the risks and consequences of debt. Budgeting ($r = .207$, $p < .05$) and saving ($r = .157$, $p < .05$) were also positively related to debt awareness, though with smaller effect sizes. Inter-correlations among the components themselves were generally weak, implying that each aspect of financial literacy contributes uniquely to students' debt awareness.

Research Question 3: To what extent do financial literacy (budgeting, saving, spending, and money management), as promoted through school counsellors, jointly predict students' debt awareness in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

Table 4.2: Summary of Regression for the Joint Contribution of Financial Literacy Components to the Prediction of Debt Awareness

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	25.889	4	6.472	22.173	.000(a)
Residual	56.947	195	0.292		
Total	82.836	199			

R = 0.560, R² = 0.313, Adjusted R² = 0.298, Std. Error = 0.540

The regression analysis in Table 4.3 examined the predictive influence of school counsellor-led financial literacy initiatives on students' understanding of the risks and consequences of debt. The result yielded a coefficient of multiple regression $R = 0.560$ and a multiple R-square of 0.313. This indicates that financial literacy initiatives (budgeting, saving, spending, and money management) combined explained for 31.3% (Adj. $R^2 = .298$) of the variance in students' debt awareness, while the remaining 68.7% is attributable to other factors not included in this study.

The ANOVA result further confirmed that there was a significant combined effect of students' perception of school counsellors' financial literacy education on debt awareness, $F(4,195) = 22.173$, $p < 0.001$. This suggests that students who perceived their counsellors as actively teaching them about budgeting, saving, spending, and money management were significantly more likely to report awareness of the risks and consequences of debt.

Research Question 4: Which financial literacy components (budgeting, saving, and responsible spending) are most emphasized by school counsellors, according to students in secondary schools in Ekiti State?

Table 4.4: Relative Contribution of Financial Literacy Components to Students' Perceptions of Counsellors' Emphasis

Predictor (IVs)	Unstandardized B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig.	Rank Contribution
(Constant)	1.215	0.143	—	8.497	.000	
Budgeting	0.314	0.071	0.421	4.401	.000	1
Saving	0.271	0.066	0.298	4.106	.000	3
Responsible Spending	0.198	0.062	0.192	3.194	.002	4
Money Management	0.385	0.073	0.372	5.274	.000	2

Table 4.4 revealed that among the components of financial literacy, budgeting ($\beta = .421$, $p < .001$) made the strongest contribution, followed by money management ($\beta = .372$, $p < .001$), while saving ($\beta = .298$, $p < .001$) also showed significant influence. Spending ($\beta = .192$, $p < .01$) made the least contribution but remained a significant predictor. This suggests that students perceive counsellors to emphasize practical financial planning (budgeting and money management) more strongly than saving or spending practices in promoting debt awareness. This indicates that school counsellors are perceived to focus more on budgeting skills, while still giving considerable attention to saving

and responsible spending. Collectively, these elements shape how students internalize financial literacy guidance in secondary schools.

5 DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide new insights into the role of school counsellors in promoting financial literacy and debt awareness among secondary school students in Ekiti State. The results from students' perceptions indicate that counsellors are moderately engaged in teaching financial skills such as saving, budgeting, spending, and money management. Notably, saving emerged as the area most reinforced during counselling sessions, while goal-setting and long-term planning received comparatively less emphasis. This finding aligns with Adeleke and Igbinedion (2023), who reported that Nigerian students often engage in day-to-day money decisions but lack structured financial goal orientation due to limited counselling focus.

The correlation results further highlight that all financial literacy components budgeting, saving, responsible spending, and money management used in the study are positively associated with students' debt awareness. Among these, money management and responsible spending showed the strongest relationships with debt awareness, suggesting that practical skills in handling daily finances and controlling expenditure enhance students' recognition of debt risks. This finding corroborates the work of Brown et al. (2014), which established that young people with stronger spending discipline and money management competencies are less likely to engage in harmful borrowing.

Furthermore, the findings revealed that students' perceptions of counsellor-led financial literacy initiatives had a significant effect on their awareness of debt. The result implies that students who perceived their school counsellors as effectively teaching budgeting, saving, spending, and money management also reported a greater understanding of the risks and consequences of debt. In line with earlier studies (e.g., Adeyemi & Oyenuga, 2021; Olowookere, 2022), the perception of counselling support in financial literacy appears to be a critical factor in shaping how students view money management and debt. This underscores the importance of strengthening the financial literacy role of school counsellors, as students' perceptions of counsellors' involvement directly influence their readiness to make informed financial decisions and avoid unhealthy debt practices. Moreover, regression analysis revealed that budgeting was the most emphasized component by school counsellors, followed closely by money management, while responsible spending made the least contribution, though still significant. This pattern suggests that school counsellors in Ekiti State prioritize financial planning and control skills over spending habits. The result echoes Chikwendu and Etim (2023), who observed that school-based financial literacy programs were most impactful when they emphasized structured planning such as budgeting, as opposed to abstract discussions about debt. Taken together, these findings strengthen the argument that school counsellors play a unique role in equipping students with practical money skills that directly shape their perceptions and awareness of debt.

6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This study has demonstrated that school counsellors are perceived by students as important facilitators of financial literacy and debt awareness in secondary schools. By focusing on budgeting, saving, spending, and money management, counsellors contribute to students' ability

to understand, anticipate, and respond to the realities of credit and borrowing. The results show that while all components of financial literacy positively influence debt awareness, money management and responsible spending exert the strongest effects, underscoring the need for a balanced approach to financial education. Importantly, budgeting emerged as the area most emphasized by counsellors, reflecting a tendency to focus on financial planning as the foundation of debt management.

The implications of these findings are multifaceted. For policymakers, the study underscores the need to integrate financial literacy into the secondary school counselling curriculum more deliberately, ensuring that goal-setting, saving, and spending habits receive equal attention alongside budgeting. School administrators should provide capacity-building opportunities for counsellors, equipping them with resources and digital tools to address emerging financial challenges, such as mobile lending apps that increasingly expose adolescents to credit risks (Nwachukwu & Daramola, 2022). Counsellors themselves must broaden their scope of guidance beyond academic and career counselling to include structured, real-world financial education that students can apply immediately.

Finally, for researchers, this study highlights the importance of further exploring how financial literacy interventions delivered through counselling shape long-term debt behaviour among adolescents. Longitudinal studies could reveal whether skills taught in school counselling sessions persist into adulthood and help reduce the prevalence of unhealthy borrowing practices in Nigeria. By equipping young people early with the tools for responsible money management, school counsellors can make a lasting contribution to building a financially aware generation.

7. DECLARATIONS

The authors declare that this paper, titled "*Students' Perceptions of School Counsellors' Role in Financial Literacy and Debt Awareness in Secondary Schools in Ekiti State*", is based on original research. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the authors upon reasonable request. The authors also confirm that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the conduct, analysis, or reporting of this research.

8. LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This study was limited to secondary school students in Ekiti State, with data collected through self-reported questionnaires. As such, the findings may not fully capture the perceptions of students in other states or reflect long-term behavioural outcomes. Future research could expand the scope by including a comparative analysis across different regions, or by incorporating qualitative approaches such as interviews and focus groups to provide deeper insights. Moreover, studies that examine the perspectives of school counsellors themselves, alongside parents and teachers, could yield a more comprehensive understanding of how financial literacy and debt awareness are nurtured among students.

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